

Erratum to *Odonatologica* 44 (3): 349-374

**Contrasting life-history patterns between
vernal pond specialists and hydroperiod generalists
in *Lestes* damselflies
(Odonata: Lestidae)**

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Erratum. Due to a miscalculation, wrong data about growth rate has been presented in the study by SCHIEL & BUCHWALD (2015). Therefore, the following sentences are not correct and must be deleted: »d) higher growth rates in *L. dryas* and *L. barbarus* than in the other species« (p. 349); »d) highest growth rates in *L. dryas* and *L. barbarus*.« (p. 370).

On p. 361, the second paragraph is to be corrected the following way:

“Growth rate, as a measure unit for increase of size in time, differed significantly between species (Kruskal-Wallis test, $p < 0.0001$). Growth rate of vernal pond specialist *L. macrostigma* was significantly higher than those of all other species (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p < 0.0001$) (Fig. 7). *Lestes viridis* had the second highest growth rate followed by that of *L. virens*, *L. barbarus*, *L. sponsa*, and *L. dryas* (Fig. 7). In a pairwise comparison the growth rates of *L. barbarus* and *L. sponsa* and those of *L. macrostigma* and *L. viridis* did not differ significantly (Mann-Whitney U-test, $p > 0.005$).”

Figure 7 is to be replaced by the following:

Figure 7. Growth rates of six *Lestes* species. Bars identified with different letters differ significantly. Vernal pond species are shaded.

SCHIEL F.-J. & BUCHWALD R. 2015. Contrasting life-history patterns between vernal pond specialists and hydroperiod generalists in *Lestes* damselflies (Odonata: Lestidae). *Odonatologica* **44**: 349-374